

EVALUATION OF THE PERCEIVED SERVICE QUALITY OF SPECIAL SPORT CENTER ORIENTED AT RECREATION ACCORDING TO SOME VARIABLES

Harun Ayar¹

High School of Physical Education
and Sports Recreation,
Gelişim University, İstanbul, Turkey

Abstract:

The aim of this study is evaluating the service quality that individuals perceive according to some certain variabilities in special sport centers. While the population includes the members of sport centers in Edirne, the sample includes the members of a sport center named Sports Montana. There are 94 males and 21 females in this study which has total 115 individuals. During the collection of data, I benefit from The Service Quality of Sport-Fitness Centers in Turkey which has been developed by Ucan and Dogu in 2007. The participants has evaluated the survey consisted total 31 articles and 6 aspects via five point likert scale. Tests of frequencies, descriptive, cross tabs, Kruskal Wallis, Mann Whitney U have helped this study. Eventually, participants are different from each other in the way of sex, exercise type, level of income. So, their perceptions of quality vary.

Keywords: fitness, sports, perceived service quality, recreation, leisure time

1. Introduction

Service is all kinds of events which have the features of meeting the requirements and is consumed at the same time it is produced. It is also a complement of non-physical activities that are sold with a certain price and need no possession of a goods with the aim of meeting the requirements, taking advantage and satisfaction.

Survey of the service quality constitutes the first step of the improvement and development of its quality, if a business gets true information about the current service quality level; it can take action to future needs (Eleren and others, 2007). Hence, service business have to develop various methods to test their customers' perceives about the quality. This survey is easy with working systematically. The differences between

¹ Correspondence: email hayar@gelisim.edu.tr

perceives and expectations of customers about the service quality has gained acceptance as the survey index (Ersöz and others 2009).

Today's increasing competition circumstances make the similar business focus on the service quality and customer satisfaction to survive and earn a profit (Serarslan and Kepoğlu, 2006). Both increasing demand to sport and physical activities and spreading this kind of business have created competition (Yıldız, 2012). The fact is that sport business has to develop customer-oriented strategies to survive in this competitive world. While successful business stays alive, others have to stand back from market. This situation brings up the effects of service quality on the customer and causes efforts based on customer to get their satisfaction.

Service has been defined as economic activities that provide benefit and create values for customers in special times and places (Lovelock, 2000). Customer satisfaction forms when performance of product reaches the expectation and it has a key effect on the next buying behavior. Pleased customer buys the same product again and shares his/her experiences with other people (Kotler and Armstrong, 2004).

When we deal with the service quality in sport, this concept is described in more abstract factors. We can define sport services as a complement of activities which gain favor people to fun, reduce stress, being healthy, looking good, socializing etc. The classification of sport services is an important factor to understand the meaning of sport services. It can be categorized in two different aspects according to the type of participation. These aspects are named as sport services based on watching and attendance (Çimen and Gürbüz, 2007).

Recreational aimed sport services can be evaluated in these two categories below. Recreational aimed sport is one the most preferred fields. Because this kind of sport is the ability to response the every needs of individuals from all ages and sexes. Sport offers people some alternatives with its features, diversities, sense of community in open or indoor areas. Today when people care about nature, adventure, beauty and health etc. sport has become an important recreation mediator.

2. Method

2.1 Study Group

The aim of this study is evaluating the service quality and data have been collected by using random sampling method. Sample consists of member of a fitness center which is engaged in commercial activity in Edirne. With the permission of the director, we give active members these surveys. There are 350 individuals; however, only 150 of them want to be volunteer. As a result, we have evaluated 115 surveys which are filled out completely. Feedback correlation is %70.

2.2 Scale Instrument

Ucan and Dogu have developed Scale of The Service Quality of Sport-Fitness Centers in Turkey with the aim of evaluating the service quality of sport centers Scale of The Service Quality of Sport-Fitness Centers consists of interaction quality, outcome quality,

physical environment quality, exerciser equipment, program quality, ambient conditions, which are total 31 article and 6 aspects. Reliability analysis of this scale has shown the Cronbach's alpha is 0,93. This proves that the scale is reliable. Five point likert scale has been used to evaluate the statements in the scale. Results are limited to 115 individuals who are volunteer and member of the fitness center. Another limit is that the survey involves only Edirne Province due to some other problems such as time, lack of money and difficulty in getting permission from the directors of some fitness centers. Therefore, the results do not represent the service quality of all fitness centers in Turkey.

Table 1: Members' Demographic Information

		N	%
Age	15-25	75	65.2
	26-35	40	34,8
	Total	115	100
Sex	Male	94	81.7
	Female	21	18.3
	Total	115	100
Educational Level	High Schools and Their Equivalents	23	20.0
	Undergraduate	85	73.0
	Master Degree	8	7.0
	Total	115	100
Level of Income	0-1000TL	30	26.1
	1001-2000TL	31	27.0
	2001-3000TL	28	24.3
	3001TL and over	26	22.6
	Total	115	100
The Purpose of Being in Fitness Center?	Healthy Life	71	61.7
	Recreation	15	13.0
	Successful in Sport	29	25.2
	Total	115	100
Which Are The Workouts You Do?	Fitness	77	67.0
	Cross fit	23	20.0
	Crunch	15	13.0
	Total	115	100
Exercise Duration	1-3 Months	42	36.5
	4-6 Months	24	20.9
	7-12 Months	13	11.3
	+12 Months	36	31.3
	Total	115	100

When we look at the demographic information about the members, we can see that most of the participants are between 15-25 years (%65,2), male (%81,7), their educational levels are undergraduate (%73,0), their level of income and exercise duration are almost similar, their purpose is being healthy (%61,7), they usually do fitness (%67,0).

3. Results

Table 2: The Mean and Standard Deviation Value of Perceived Service Quality and Dimensions

Perceived Service Quality	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean±Sd
Interaction Quality	115	10,00	50,00	45,51±5,96
Outcome Quality	115	5,00	25,00	23,67±3,10
Physical Environment Quality	115	7,00	35,00	28,37±5,45
Exerciser Equipment	115	3,00	15,00	11,65±3,18
Program Quality	115	3,00	15,00	12,90±2,64
Ambient Conditions Quality	115	3,00	15,00	12,76±2,31
Total	115	31,00	155,00	134,87±17,45

In Table 2, participants' interaction quality (45,51), outcome quality (23,66), physical environment quality (28,37), program quality (12,90), ambient conditions quality (12,90) are defined as high level. However, exerciser equipment (11,65) are lower. On this results, the perception of outcome quality is the highest but the perception of exerciser equipment quality is the lowest.

Table 3: Evaluation of the Members' Perceive of Service Quality According to Sex Variable

Sub-Dimensions	Sex	N	Mean	P
Interaction Quality	Male	94	57,69	,827
	Female	21	59,40	
Outcome Quality	Male	94	57,37	,600
	Female	21	60,83	
Physical Environment Quality	Male	94	56,90	,452
	Female	21	62,93	
Exerciser Equipment	Male	94	54,91	,034*
	Female	21	71,81	
Program Quality	Male	94	56,65	,345
	Female	21	64,05	
Ambient Conditions Quality	Male	94	58,40	,779
	Female	21	56,19	
Total	Male	94	56,46	,293
	Female	21	64,90	

P<0,05

The perceived service quality in fitness center differs by sexes of participants. This diversity has been shown in exerciser equipment sub-dimensions.

Harun Ayar
EVALUATION OF THE PERCEIVED SERVICE QUALITY OF SPECIAL SPORT CENTER
ORIENTED AT RECREATION ACCORDING TO SOME VARIABLES

Table 4: Evaluation of the Members' Perceive of Service Quality According to Workout Types

Sub-Dimensions	Types of Workouts	N	Mean±Sd	Df	P	Division
Interaction Quality	Fitness ¹	77	45,31±6,66	2	,759	
	Cross fit ²	23	46,26±4,30			
	Crunch ³	15	45,40±4,71			
Outcome Quality	Fitness ¹	77	23,19±3,66		,054	
	Cross fit ²	23	24,47±1,08			
	Crunch ³	15	24,86±0,35			
Physical Environment Quality	Fitness ¹	77	28,14±5,83		,971	
	Cross fit ²	23	28,86±4,97			
	Crunch ³	15	28,80±4,17			
Exerciser Equipments	Fitness ¹	77	11,22±3,40		,161	
	Crossfit ²	23	12,26±2,87			
	Crunch ³	15	12,93±1,79			
Program Quality	Fitness ¹	77	12,42±3,02		,035	1-2
	Crossfit ²	23	14,17±0,93			
	Crunch ³	15	13,40±1,40			
Ambient Conditions Quality	Fitness ¹	77	12,57±2,47		,494	
	Crossfit ²	23	13,04±2,09			
	Crunch ³	15	13,26±1,75			
Total	Fitness ¹	77	132,87±19,56		,414	
	Crossfit ²	23	139,08±12,36			
	Crunch ³	15	138,66±9,77			

P<0,05

There are significant diversities in program quality sub-dimension according to workout types that members do participate. This diversity is in between fitness and cross fit workouts.

Table 5: Evaluation of the Members' Perceive of Service Quality According to Level of Income

Sub-Dimensions	Level of Income	N	Mean±Sd	Df	P	Division
Interaction Quality	0-1000TL ¹	30	42,53±5,62	3	,000	1-4
	1001TL-2000TL ²	31	43,96±8,14			1-3
	2001TL-3000TL ³	28	49,00±2,89			2-3
	3001TL and Over ⁴	26	47,03±2,70			
Outcome Quality	0-1000TL ¹	30	24,13±1,63		,538	
	1001TL-2000TL ²	31	23,41±3,72			
	2001TL-3000TL ³	28	24,17±1,56			
	3001TL and Over ⁴	26	22,88±4,51			
Physical Environment Quality	0-1000TL ¹	30	27,56±4,33		,001	1-3
	1001TL-2000TL ²	31	28,61±5,69			3-4
	2001TL-3000TL ³	28	31,53±3,02			
	3001TL and Over ⁴	26	25,61±6,70			
Exerciser Equipments	0-1000TL ¹	30	11,73±2,11		,001	1-3
	1001TL-2000TL ²	31	10,61±3,72			2-3
	2001TL-3000TL ³	28	13,60±1,85			4-3

Harun Ayar
EVALUATION OF THE PERCEIVED SERVICE QUALITY OF SPECIAL SPORT CENTER
ORIENTED AT RECREATION ACCORDING TO SOME VARIABLES

	3001TL and Over ⁴	26	10,69±3,76		
Program Quality	0-1000TL ¹	30	13,23±1,43	,236	
	1001TL-2000TL ²	31	12,70±3,45		
	2001TL-3000TL ³	28	13,46±1,77		
	3001TL and Over ⁴	26	12,15±3,28		
Ambient Conditions Quality	0-1000TL ¹	30	12,66±2,03	,000	1-3
	1001TL-2000TL ²	31	11,67±2,71		2-3
	2001TL-3000TL ³	28	14,39±1,10		4-3
	3001TL and Over ⁴	26	12,38±2,22		
Total	0-1000TL ¹	30	131,86±12,14	,000	
	1001TL-2000TL ²	31	131,00±22,62		1-3
	2001TL-3000TL ³	28	146,17±9,31		2-3
	3001TL and Over ⁴	26	130,76±17,89		4-3

The level of income results show that, participants who has 2001-3000 TL and 3001 TL and over income are more satisfied with the service quality than the ones have 0-1000 TL income. Also the ones who have 2001-3000TL income are more satisfied with the service quality than the ones having 1001-2000TL income In physical environment quality sub-dimension, individuals who have 0-1000 TL level of income find the service quality better than ones having 2001-3000TL level of income, besides participants having 2001-3000 TL level of income find the service quality better than ones having 3001 and over level of income. In exerciser equipment, ambient conditions quality and total perceived service quality sub-dimensions, participants who have 0-1000 TL, 1001-2000 TL, 3001TL and over level of income find the service quality worse than ones having 2001-3000TL level of income.

Table 6: Evaluation of the Members' Perceive of Service Quality According to Exercise Duration

Sub-dimensions	Exercise Duration	N	Mean±Sd	Df	P	Division
Interaction Quality	1-3 months ¹	42	45,83±4,74	3	,000	1-4
	4-6 months ²	24	41,33±8,32			1-2
	7-12 months ³	13	43,23±6,31			2-4
	12 months and over ⁴	36	48,75±2,37			3-4
Outcome Quality	1-3 months ¹	42	22,66±3,60	3	,000	1-2
	4-6 months ²	24	23,58±4,30			1-4
	7-12 months ³	13	24,30±1,54			
	12 months and over ⁴	36	24,66±0,89			
Physical Environment Quality	1-3 months ¹	42	28,33±6,33	3	,000	1-2
	4-6 months ²	24	25,20±5,68			2-4
	7-12 months ³	13	27,07±4,19			
	12 months and over ⁴	36	31,00±2,81			
Exerciser Equipments	1-3 months ¹	42	11,95±3,51	3	,000	1-4
	4-6 months ²	24	10,58±2,94			2-4
	7-12 months ³	13	8,61±2,93			3-4
	12 months and over ⁴	36	13,11±1,86			
Program Quality	1-3 months ¹	42	12,35±3,27	3	,076	
	4-6 months ²	24	12,50±2,84			

Harun Ayar
EVALUATION OF THE PERCEIVED SERVICE QUALITY OF SPECIAL SPORT CENTER
ORIENTED AT RECREATION ACCORDING TO SOME VARIABLES

	7-12 months ³	13	14,15±1,40		
	12 months and over ⁴	36	13,36±1,74		
Ambient Conditions Quality	1-3 months ¹	42	12,35±2,02	,000	1-4
	4-6 months ²	24	11,70±2,56		2-4
	7-12 months ³	13	10,84±2,40		3-4
	12 months and over ⁴	36	14,61±0,76		
Total	1-3 months ¹	42	133,50±17,42	,000	1-4
	4-6 months ²	24	124,91±22,29		2-4
	7-12 months ³	13	128,23±13,15		3-4
	12 months and over ⁴	36	145,50±6,93		

In the interaction quality sub-dimension, the results show that participants who workout with the aim of recreative and exercise for 1-3 months have less sense of service quality than the ones who exercise for 13 months and over have. Participants who exercise for 1-3 months have much sense of service quality than the ones who exercise for 4-6 months have. Participants who exercise for 4-6 and 7-12 months have less sense of service quality than the ones who exercise for 12 months and over have. In the outcome quality sub-dimension, individuals who exercise for 1-3 months have less sense of service quality than the ones who exercise for 4-6 and 12 and over months. In physical environment quality sub-dimension, individuals who exercise for 1-3 months have higher perception about the service quality than the ones exercise for 4-6 months. Participants who continue to fitness center for 4-6 months have less sense of service quality than the ones who continue for 12 months and over. In exerciser equipment and ambient conditions sub-dimensions, participants who exercise for 12 months and over find the service quality better than the ones exercise for 1-3, 4-6 and 7-12 months do.

4. Discussion and Result

When we consider the demographic information of participants, most of them are 15-25 years old (%65,2). In the study which Akkoyun (2015) did in Elazığ Province, 15-25 years old participant consist of %17,0 of all. Most of them are males (%81,7), their educational levels are undergraduate (%73,0), their level of income are similar, their purpose is being healthy (%61,7), they usually do fitness (%67,0) and there isn't significant division between their exercise durations.

When we look forward to table 2 and it's sub-dimensions' mean and standard deviation values, we can conclude that physical environment quality, ambient conditions quality, exerciser equipment quality, program quality, interaction quality and outcome(result) quality are good. This shows that individuals who participate this survey are satisfied with the service quality.

The perceived service quality in fitness center differs by the participants' sexes. In exerciser equipment sub-dimension, female participants have better service quality than males. Akkoyun (2015) and Üzümlü and others (2016) have found significant differences about the physical environment conditions sub-dimension according to

male and female participants' perception of service quality. However, this does not show similarity with the study.

In program quality sub-dimension of participants' workout types, there is significant difference. This difference is between fitness and cross fit. Individuals who participate the cross fit exercise have much sense of program quality than the ones who participate fitness exercise have.

There is significant difference between the perceptions of service quality of individuals according to their level of income. These differences are shown in sub-dimensions of interaction quality, physical environment quality, exerciser equipment, ambient conditions quality and total service quality. Yüzgenç and Özgül (2014), have found a significant difference in service quality sub-dimension. It corresponds to current study. However, Akkoyun (2015) has found a significant difference in ambient condition sub-dimension. This study does not show similarity with the current study. There aren't significant differences in outcome quality and program quality sub-dimensions.

In fitness centers, there are significant differences in all aspects and total perceived service quality except program quality according to exercise durations of individuals.

As a result, individuals who exercise with the aim of recreation have different perceptions according to some significant differences. This sport center cares about the female oriented equipment and prepare better program to the individuals who do cross fit exercise than the others. Members who have 2001-3000TL level of income have better sense of service quality and the ones who exercise for 12 months and over find the service quality better than the ones who exercise for under 12 months.

Bibliography

1. Serarslan, M.Z. ve Kepoğlu, A. (2006). Spor Örgütlerinde Toplam Kalite Yönetimi. İstanbul: Morpa Kültür Yayınları.
2. Yıldız, S.M. (2012). Instruments for Measuring Service Quality in Sport and Physical Activity Services. *Collegium Antropologicum*, 36(2), 689–696.
3. Yıldız, S.M. And Tüfekçi, Ö. (2010). Assessment Of Expectations And Perceptions Of Fitness Center Customers For Service Quality. *Balikesir University the Institute of Social Sciences*, 13(24), 1–11.
4. Lovelock, C. (2000). *Services Marketing: People, Technology, Strategy*. 4th Edition, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
5. Parasuraman, A, Zeithaml, V.A., And Berry, L.L. (1994). Reassessment Of Expectations As A Comparison Standard On Measuring Service Quality: Implications For Further Research. *Journal Of Marketing*, 58(1), 111–124.
6. Kotler, P. And Armstrong, G. (2004). *Principles Of Marketing*. Pearson Prenticehall.

7. Çimen, Z., Gürbüz, B. (2007). Spor Hizmetlerinde Toplam Kalite Yönetimi. Alp Yayınevi, Ankara.
8. Karaküçük, S. (2005). Rekreasyon: Boş Zamanları Değerlendirme. Gazi Kitabevi, Ankara.
9. Yıldız Y. Onağ AO. Onağ Z (2013). Spor Ve Rekreasyon Hizmetlerinde Algılanan Hizmet Kalitesinin İncelenmesi: Fitness Merkezi Örneği. Uluslararası Hakemli Beşeri Ve Akademik Bilimler Dergisi, 2(3):114-130.
10. Eleren, A., Bektaş, Ç., Görmüş, A. Ş. (2007). "Hizmet Sektöründe Hizmet Kalitesinin Servqual Yöntemi İle Ölçülmesi Ve Hazır Yemek İşletmesinde Bir Uygulama". Finans Politik&Ekonomik Yorumlar, 44(514): 75-88.
11. Ersöz, S., Pinarbaşı, M., Türker, A.K., Yüzükirmizi, M. (2009). "Hizmet Kalitesinin Servqual Metodu İle Ölçümü Ve Sonuçlarının Yapısal Eşitlik Modelleri İle Analizi: Öğretmen Evi Uygulaması". International Journal Of Research & Development, 1(1): 19-27.
12. Akkoyun, İ. (2015). Yerel Yönetimlere Ait Fitness Merkezlerinde Algılanan Hizmet Kalitesi (Elazığ İl Örneği), Fırat Üniversitesi, Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Yüksek Lisans Tezi.
13. Üzüm, H., Yeşildağ, B., Karlı, Ü., Ünlü, H., Parlar, F., Çokpartal, C., Tekin, N., (2016). Kamu Ve Özel Spor Merkezleri Müşterilerinin Hizmet Kalitesi Algılarının İncelenmesi, AİBÜ Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi, Cilt 16, Yıl 16, Sayı: 3, 16: 167-180.
14. Uçan, Y. (2007). Spor-Fitness Merkezlerinin Algılanan Hizmet Kalitesi Ölçeğinin Geliştirilmesi, Abant İzzet Baysal Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Üniversitesi, Yüksek Lisans Tezi.
15. Yüzgeç, A.A., Veözü, S.A. (2014). Yerel Yönetimlerin Sunduğu Spor Hizmetlerinde Hizmet Kalitesi (Gençlik Merkezleri Ve Aile Yaşam Gençlik Merkezleri Örneği), Spor Bilimleri Dergisi, Hacettepe J. Of Sport Science 25 (2).

Harun Ayar
EVALUATION OF THE PERCEIVED SERVICE QUALITY OF SPECIAL SPORT CENTER
ORIENTED AT RECREATION ACCORDING TO SOME VARIABLES

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).